

EIJASTR

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF APPLIED SCIENCES AND THEORETICAL RESEARCH

International Scientific Journal

2026

European International Journal Of Applied Sciences And Theoretical Research

Volume 02, Issue 05

EDITORIAL BOARD:**Professor Emma Franke**

Editor in Chief

Prof. Jo Coldwell-Neilson

Associate Editor In Chief Deakin University, Australia

Mr Mohd Helmy

Abd Wahab Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Shafi'i Muhammad Abdulhamid

Federal University Of Technology Minna, Nigeria., Nigeria

Dr Man Fung (Kelvin) Lo

The Chinese University Of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Dr Ahmad Samed

Al-Adwan Al Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Waleed Alsabhan

Kacst, Saudi Arabia Yvonne Antonucci Widener University, United States

Prof. Orit Avidov Ungar

Achva Academic College & Open University Of Israel, Israel

Dr. Aslina Baharum

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia

CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF ENGINEERING THINKING AND ACTIVITY

Mukhitdin Nazarov

Andijan State Technical Institute

Associate Professor of the Department of Languages and Humanities,

candidate of philosophical sciences

Abstract. This article examines the historical formation of engineering thinking and activity, as well as considerations regarding its study as a science. Attention is paid to the necessity of combining comprehensive technical and theoretical knowledge in the training of a future engineer. At the same time, it is emphasized that the humanization of technical education is not exempt from relying on teachings that must be formed in an engineer, such as ethics and aesthetics.

Keywords: engineering, freedom of activity, ethics, aesthetic education, humanities, worldview, technical education, objective, methodology, genetic engineering.

Introduction. An analysis of pedagogical literature and practice shows that engineering education has several serious shortcomings. One problem has long been the narrow specialization of engineers. One of the prominent representatives of engineering education, Professor A. Ridler, noted at the beginning of the last century that the task of a higher technical school is not only to train chemists, electricians, mechanics, etc., that is, specialists who never leave their limited field, but also to provide the engineer with a multifaceted education and create opportunities for mastering neighboring fields. The second problem, on the contrary, is not sufficiently deeply understood: our higher educational institutions, while preparing future engineers, are essentially oriented toward the image of the engineer of the second half of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century. The fact is that modern engineering activities have become more complex and equipped not only with computer technology but also with non-traditional tasks requiring new engineering thinking.

Methods. Non-traditional types of engineering activity and thinking are characterized by the following specific features:

1) the connection between engineering aspects of activity and social, economic, and environmental aspects. Currently, an engineer must develop (design and manufacture) not only simple technical products—that is, machines, mechanisms, and devices—but also complex systems. However, these systems, in addition to technical subsystems, include other non-technical systems, the development of which

involves addressing disciplines such as engineering psychology, design, engineering economics, applied ecology, and sociology;

2) the necessity of modeling and calculating not only the main processes of the designed engineering facility but also the possible, especially negative, consequences of its operation. Such consequences are usually of three types: changes in the environment and nature under the influence of new technology, changes in activities and infrastructure (for example, the introduction of new aviation equipment necessitates the creation of new enterprises, design bureaus, educational programs, and the allocation of resources), and finally, "anthropogenic changes," i.e., the impact of new technology on humans: changes in their needs, living conditions, etc.;

3) a new feature of engineering thinking. It implies a higher general culture of the engineer's personality, the use in their work of modern methodology and the concepts and methods of the applied humanities.

The third problem is how to prevent the engineering corps from being oriented exclusively toward the ideals of natural-scientific thinking, or more broadly, toward a technical culture. The opposition between technical and humanitarian cultures is well known. Representatives of technical culture proceed from the view that the world is subject to the laws of nature, which can be understood and then put at the service of man. Representatives of technical culture are convinced that rational relations operate in the world, that everything (including man) can be designed and constructed, and that phenomena are objective and "transparent" (i.e., their nature and structure can be understood by man sooner or later). Such ideas ultimately inspire genetic engineers, the designers of large systems, politicians who promise humanity continuous scientific and technological progress and increased prosperity, and, finally, ordinary consumers who are convinced that the nature of our planet is designed to live in favorable conditions and abundance, and therefore it is necessary to "equip" it with enterprises, cities, machines, and structures as soon as possible. In modern civilization, technical culture is undoubtedly the mass, leading culture, while humanitarian culture stands in opposition to it. A person with a humanitarian orientation refuses to recognize that the life of mankind, society, or nature is determined by science and technology. He is convinced that both man and nature are spiritual entities whose existence cannot be measured by the yardstick of technical culture. He views all of them as living subjects, believing that it is important to understand them, listen to them, and speak with them, but it is impossible to manipulate them or turn them into tools. A person with a humanitarian orientation values the past, lives a full life in it, and approaches other people and communication not as socio-psychological phenomena, but as the element of their own life.

Deep specialization and socialization in these two cultures ultimately lead to the formation of two types of people with different worldviews, lifestyles, and attitudes toward the environment. To an engineer, a person with a humanitarian orientation appears to be from another planet (because, despite living in a world of technical civilization, he does not want to recognize this world), and in the

humanities, a person oriented toward technology leaves an unusual impression (a technical person and a technical world resemble a rational device, a frightening or, conversely, a convenient machine).

Results. Today, the issue of the humanization of technical education is on the agenda. At the same time, various points of view have been put forward, one of which implies that philosophy, sociology, theory and history of culture, psychology and other humanities should be taught in technical universities, while another believes that humanities education is determined not by the study of humanities, but by a special approach to reality, a special way of thinking and a special worldview. Proponents of the second approach, citing arguments in favor of their point of view, often refer to the experience of the USA, where future scientists and engineers listen to relevant humanities and courses or, at their discretion, study some humanitarian topic such as "Features of Medieval Japanese Poetry" or "French Literature of the 19th Century." But neither viewpoint has a solid foundation.

In the first case, it is unclear why teaching casual humanities helps an engineer think and imagine differently. Furthermore, existing pedagogical experience shows that students do not fully understand why they need such humanitarian knowledge. In the second case, there is no answer to the question of which humanities and how to teach them in order to form the humanities-oriented personality of an engineer. In general, in our view, it is inappropriate to link the issue of the humanization of technical education with the teaching of humanities in technical universities. Here, it is necessary to approach the question more broadly: what should engineering education be so that it meets the requirements of the times and the engineering profession, the characteristics and trends of modern engineering, the specifics of the modern educational process, and the general requirements and ideals of post-industrial man?

Since the separation of technical and humanitarian cultures leads to a further exacerbation of the crisis of our civilization, it is necessary to work toward their rapprochement and to strive for the development of a unified humanitarian-technical personality. The ideal is a holistic, perfect person who is oriented in both cultures and is considered the "seed" of a new culture, free from the "humanitarian-technical" opposition. In general, the situations indicated here determine one of the content of humanitarian education. The second content of humanities education is professional and implies that future engineers and other specialists in the field of technical sciences must master specific specialized knowledge and methods in the field of humanities.

Conclusion. An analysis of the current state of engineering education shows that the training of a modern engineer should not be limited to providing technical knowledge within a narrow field. The increasing complexity of engineering activities, which are closely linked to social, environmental, and human factors, requires comprehensive, systematic, and critical thinking from the engineer. From this perspective, the humanization of engineering education—that is, its enrichment with humanities, ethical, and aesthetic perspectives—is a requirement of the times.

However, existing approaches to how humanities knowledge should be integrated into technical education (approaches focused solely on teaching subjects or shaping a worldview) lack sufficient clarity and validity. Therefore, the issue of humanizing engineering education should be approached not in a narrow framework, but broadly, taking into account the needs of modern society, trends in technical development, and the ideals of a post-industrial person.

Today, overcoming the gaps between technical and humanitarian cultures and forming a comprehensively developed, comprehensively thinking engineer who deeply understands their responsibility to society through their integration is an important task. Such an approach not only enriches the educational process but also plays an important role in preventing global civilizational crises.

References

1. Bazhikhanov, A. A. *Philosophy of Engineering: Basic Concepts and Approaches*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan University Press. — 2015.
2. Shamsiev, S. S. *Philosophy of Engineering and Technology*. Tashkent: Science and Technology Publishing House. - 2012.
3. Alimov, A. S. *Engineering and Social Responsibility*. Tashkent: National University of Uzbekistan Publishing House. - 2020.